

DISTANCE MODULAR LEARNING FOR GRADE 10 ELECTRONICS: ITS IMPLICATION TO LEARNERS' ACHIEVEMENT AND ATTITUDE

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Distance Modular Learning for Grade 10 Electronics: Its Implication to Learners' Achievement and Attitude

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Abstract

This research is a mixed method study utilized the quantitative approach in gathering the data needed for the study which included 64 students that constitutes to the total population of learners. Findings reveal that learners improve their achievement through the use of print materials, as well as the materials per se. Sense of responsibility and independency develop in them even with no to limited teacher-physical support to them since face-to-face instruction is not possible. While attitude and achievement are relative in many aspects, as proven in various studies and researches. Moreover, print modular instruction alone can possibly and positively effect to a learner.

Keywords: *achievement and attitude, distance modular learning*

Introduction

At present, new modalities are being developed as a form of response to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. These new teaching and learning modalities are now being integrated in order to continue the pursuit for education. With it are new paradigms such as blended learning approaches are now being integrated to address learner needs.

The K to 12 curriculums is a program of the government that gives emphasis on academic and vocational tracks which sustain a continuum toward preparation for higher tertiary education and skills development qualifications for National Certificates I, II and III. The newly implemented curriculum has its overarching goal is the holistic development of every Filipino learner with 21st century skills who is adequately prepared for work, entrepreneurship, middle level skills development and higher education (Camarao, 2003).

The overarching goal of the K to 12 programs proves that the teaching of TLE plays a very important role in the realization of the overall goal of the curriculum. Technology and Livelihood Education in the Junior High School program particularly on Grades 7-8 are exploratory in nature. In the said curriculum, exploratory courses are designed to focus on five basic common competencies.

This includes the use of tools, equipment and paraphernalia, maintenance of tools, equipment and paraphernalia, performance of mensuration and calculation, interpretation of drawings and plans and, the practice of occupational safety and health procedures.

The researcher of this study, who is a Junior High School teacher believes that the findings of this venture will benefit the school and its teachers. Moreover, giving emphasis on issues concerning the achievement and attitude of Grade 9 students is necessary to find ways to address emergent issues regarding the students' learning on the subject. Thus, this study has been conceptualized.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the satisfaction of the Junior High School learner's assessment on their satisfaction towards school facilities and services during the transition to single shift face - to - face and blended learning classes. Specially, this research study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the learner's profile in terms of grade level?
2. What is the level satisfaction of the learners in terms of tangibles; responsiveness; empathy; assurance; reliability; and satisfaction?
3. Is there a significant difference in the learner's profile when grouped according to grade level?
4. What are the experiences of the learners during the implementation of single shift face - to - face and blended learning modality.
5. Based from the findings of the study, what plan of actions may be proposed to improve the learning delivery in school?

Literature Review

According to Calanog (2019) in her study on challenges in teaching exploratory courses of technology and livelihood education using pedagogical approaches, among the learning areas, the Technology and Livelihood Education as a subject is the most experiential, interactive, interdisciplinary and value – laden such as cultural, aesthetic, vocational, political – economic and moral values.

In support, Palispis (2008) claims that Technology and Livelihood Education is a learning area that provides the Filipino learners the quality time to demonstrate practical knowledge and life's skills that have been gained, especially the skills of vocational efficiency and empathy. Furthermore, Technology and Livelihood Education intends to develop knowledge, skills, values and attitudes that will prepare the students for entry into the world of work. This will enable the students to gain understanding and acquire competencies in various activities as they relate to Home Economics, Agriculture Arts, Industrial Arts and Entrepreneurship. The programs of vocational

education in this country are provided for in Act Number 3377, otherwise known as the Vocational Act of 1927. Article XIV, Section 5 of the 1935 Philippine Constitution, also provides for the development of vocational efficiency. Regional Memorandum No. 233, s. 2016 regarding the implementation of pedagogical approaches mandated by the state that the curriculum shall use pedagogical approaches that are constructivist, inquiry – based, reflective, collaborative and integrative. This was designed to assist all teachers facilitating learner – centered instruction in making the curriculum relevant and in strengthening teaching and learning process that would rebound to better performance of all learners in any assessment given by Department of Education.

In connection with this, Closy (2009) claims that teachers were continuously giving much effort in teaching T.L.E to make it more interesting and meaningful to every learner with the use of applicable pedagogical approaches in every lesson. However, it is a sad note that as of now, students under Grade 7 and Grade 8 taking exploratory courses in TLE were confused on what particular courses will take when they reach the next year level. At their young age, they tend to just pick the easiest one or the available courses offered by the school. Students just rely on what they just already know for the reason that they were not exposed on the different learning tracks.

COVID–19 disturbed the world. Its detrimental factors negatively affected the constituents in particular to educational endeavor and the outcomes to teachers and to the learners. On the contrary, this is also an opportunity to extend teaching stratification to address scenarios wherein attending classes in the classrooms are deemed insignificant not unless for formative assessment, 21st pedagogies are more probably applicable whereby lectures can be done through social media through the use of blogs, group chats, emails and the like. Moreover, research–output–based teaching methods are more desirable wherein students would be taught on how to be a writer and a researcher. However, this COVID-19 demeans traditional maneuvers; hence attendance literally is not necessary. This is a resolution of vanishing the old methods of teaching; but on the other hand; modular concept has led to resolve the issue as the easiest form of learning modality in the absence of internet connection.

This COVID – 19 definitely is an uprising of a new beginning onward to educational teaching stratification but subsequently this is also threatening students of which their only avenue to attain the learning process is going to internet café where they are exposed, and prohibited for safety precautions. This virus skeptically made excuses for those who were non–focus, malingered individual either to their studies or duty. This even defying one’s authority for a reason of security, a banishment of those known with infected disease, and economically the Local Government Unit (LGU) were suppressive (Mahusay, 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

Action research focuses on generating solutions to practical problems and its ability to empower practitioners, by getting them to engage with research and the subsequent development or implementation activities which will help identify problems, seek and implement practical solutions, and systematically monitor and reflect on the process and outcomes of change (Meyer, 2000).

This action research examined the effect of distant modular learning to the achievement and attitude of Grade 10 learners on learning TLE-Electronics. One group pre–posttest design using the descriptive – comparative type was employed since it compared the data of the learner’s pre and posttest scores.

The one-group pretest-posttest design assessed the achievement of the participants on TLE – Electronics after having been subjected to modular teaching modality. the participants were considered as serving at their own controls. The underlying logic is that the pretest observation provides an estimate of their posttest status under the counterfactual model, whereby they would not have been exposed to treatment.

Participants

The participants of the study were the Grade 10 Electronics students under the advisory class of the research proponent for School Year 2020 – 2021. In order to acquire a more reliable data for the action research, total enumeration was utilized in the study to acquire 100% data completeness and accuracy from the learners.

Moreover, the research participants were the students who were enrolled in the subject when the study was conducted.

Table 1. *Population of the Research Participants*

<i>Category</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Female	42	60.61
Male	24	39.39
Total	66	100

Instrument

The researcher sought approval from the school committee. The researcher submitted his proposal to the designated school research coordinator for checking and editing with a selected panel of evaluators within the school who specialized on the same area of inquiry. Upon seeking approval from the school research committee – TEAM STAR COMES, the research was endorsed to the division office

in order to acquire a permit to fully conduct the specifics of the research.

An attitude questionnaire was adapted from Seker (2011). Some of the items in the research instrument were altered in order to suit the context of the action research. To assess the progress of the learners in relation to their achievement, scores were utilized to measure their achievement in the subject.

The table shows the result of the validation of the research instruments as evaluated by selected Head Teachers and Master Teachers. From the assessment, the instruments gained an overall rating of 3.8 which was qualitatively described as very high.

Table 2. Achievement Test Validation

Indicators	Mean	Qualitative Description
Clarity and Direction of Items	3.7	Highly Valid
Presentation and Organization of Items	3.7	Highly Valid
Suitability of Items	3.7	Highly Valid
Adequateness of the Content	3.7	Highly Valid
Attainment of Purpose	4.0	Highly Valid
Objective	4.0	Highly Valid
Scale and Evaluation of Ratings	4.0	Highly Valid
Overall Mean	3.8	Highly Valid

The researcher prepared a pretest before the distribution of modules for quarter 3. Upon distribution of the modules for quarter 3, the prepared pretest for TLE-Electronics is distributed. The researcher collected and consolidated the pretest answer sheets from the advisers after the scheduled date for retrieval of modules and answer sheets for quarter 3. The posttest was distributed to students on TLE- Electronics on scheduled distribution of modules for the quarter 4 and the posttest result was collected on scheduled date of retrieval of answer sheet and modules for quarter 4.

Procedure

To determine the levels of achievement among the Grade 10 learners in Electronics, their scores were converted to mean percent scores (MPS) and were interpreted based on the table that follows:

Table 3. Achievement Level Descriptions

Mean Percent Scores (MPS)	Level	Qualitative Description
90 – 100	Advanced	Superior performance. Have deep understanding on the topic reflected by having consistent high scores in the assessment.
75 – 89.99	Proficient	Solid academic performance. Understand the lessons/subject–matter and can work independently or with little supervision from the teacher.
Below – 75	Basic	Partial understanding of lessons/subject–matter, needs teacher’s supervision for lesson.

For attitude level, student’s scores on the participants’ self–assessment on the questionnaire that was administered was converted to mean percent scores interpreted based on the level descriptions below.

Table 4. Degree Attitude Descriptions

Level	Mean Percent Scores (MPS)	Descriptions
Strongly Agree	3.50-4.00	Positive
Agree	2.50-3.49	
Disagree	1.50-2.49	Negative
Strongly Disagree	1.00-1.49	

To determine significant differences on the achievement and attitude levels of Grade 10 learners one-sample t-test was used.

Ethical Considerations

The information acquired will be kept anonymous and will only be used for research reasons to help Bambang National High School in enhancing its single shift face - to - face modality, thus, improving the implementation of single shift face - to - face classes.

Results and Discussion

Table 5. Comparative Achievement of the Learners

Qtr	Description			Total	Grand Mean	Description
	Basic	Proficient	Advance			
Q3	52	14	0	66	65.12	Basic
Q4	23	42	1	66	76.33	Proficient

N=66 Below 75=Basic 75-89.99=Proficient 90-100=Advanced

Table 6. Attitudes of the Learners along Teaching

Attitude along Teaching	Quarter III		Quarter IV	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
I share my learning problems easily.	3.197	P	3.879	P
I am provided with help in learning activities.	3.636	P	3.803	P
Electronics lessons are fun	3.288	P	3.758	P
Electronics lessons bore me.	1.364	N	1.364	N
Mean	2.871	P	3.201	P

Note: 3.50-4.00=strongly agree/positive; 2.50-3.49=agree/positive; 1.50-2.49=disagree/negative; 1.00-1.49=strongly disagree/negative; SA=Strongly Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; A=Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; P=Positive; N=Negative

Table 7. Attitudes of the Learners along School Image

Attitude along School Image	Quarter III		Quarter IV	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
I feel lucky that I am a student of this school.	3.803	P	3.803	P
It is a privilege to study in this school.	3.803	P	3.803	P
I adequately make use of the services given at school.	3.091	P	3.788	P
I wish I were a student of another school.	1.364	N	1.364	N
Mean	3.015	P	3.190	P

Note: 3.50-4.00=strongly agree/positive; 2.50-3.49=agree/positive; 1.50-2.49=disagree/negative; 1.00-1.49=strongly disagree/negative; SA=Strongly Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; A=Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; P=Positive; N=Negative

Table 8. Attitudes of the Learners along Loneliness at School

Attitude along Loneliness at School	Quarter III		Quarter IV	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
I feel lonely in the electronics classroom.	1.333	N	1.333	N
I am not able to have a healthy communication with my electronics teacher.	1.415	N	1.415	N
My electronics teacher is only interested in hardworking students.	1.303	N	1.303	N
Mean	1.350	N	1.350	N

Note: 3.50-4.00=strongly agree/positive; 2.50-3.49=agree/positive; 1.50-2.49=disagree/negative; 1.00-1.49=strongly disagree/negative; SA=Strongly Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; A=Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; P=Positive; N=Negative

Table 9. Attitudes of the Learners along Testing and Feedback

Attitude along Testing and Feedback	Quarter III		Quarter IV	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
In electronics subject, opportunities for questioning and criticizing are provided.	3.485	P	3.485	P
Students' mistakes are corrected without offending them in our electronics class.	3.697	P	3.697	P
Exams in electronics measure my real success.	3.076	P	3.818	P
Exam questions in electronics are clear and understandable	3.621	P	3.833	P
Mean	3.470	P	3.708	P

Note: 3.50-4.00=strongly agree/positive; 2.50-3.49=agree/positive; 1.50-2.49=disagree/negative; 1.00-1.49=strongly disagree/negative; SA=Strongly Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; A=Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; P=Positive; N=Negative

Table 10. Attitudes of the Learners along Reluctance

Attitude along Reluctance	Quarter III		Quarter IV	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Communication within the family makes me feel less positive towards electronics.	1.409	N	1.409	N
My family consider my going to school unnecessary.	1.333	N	1.333	N
Negative attitudes of the people in my close circle towards school negatively affect my eagerness.	1.530	N	1.530	N
My efforts are being overlooked and this decreases my interest to study.	1.439	N	1.439	N
I feel as if I am out of the activities in most of the courses	1.333	N	1.333	N
I cannot participate in many activities in my electronics class.	1.318	N	1.318	N
Mean	1.394	N	1.394	N

Note: 3.50-4.00=strongly agree/positive; 2.50-3.49=agree/positive; 1.50-2.49=disagree/negative; 1.00-1.49=strongly disagree/negative; SA=Strongly Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; A=Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; P=Positive; N=Negative

Table 11. Summary Table of the Attitudes of the Learners

Attitude	Quarter III		Quarter IV	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Teaching	2.871	P	3.201	P
School Image	3.015	P	3.190	P
Loneliness at School	1.350	N	1.350	N
Testing and Feedback	1.394	N	1.394	N
Reluctance	1.394	N	1.394	N
Grand Mean	2.374	N	2.516	P

Note: 3.50-4.00=strongly agree/positive; 2.50-3.49=agree/positive; 1.50-2.49=disagree/negative; 1.00-1.49=strongly disagree/negative; SA=Strongly Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; A=Agree; SD=Strongly Disagree; P=Positive; N=Negative

Table 12. *Difference on the Learners' Achievements*

Variable	Mean	df	computed-t	critical-t	VD
Initial Test (Q3)	65.121	64	-25.851	1.997	Significant
Final Test (Q4)	76.333				

N=66; alpha level=0.05

Table 13. *Difference on the Learners' Attitudes*

Variable	Mean	df	computed-t	critical-t	VD
Initial Test (Q3)	2.374	64	-14.446	1.997	Significant
Final Test (Q4)	2.516				

N=66; alpha level=0.05

Table 5 displays the initial grand mean is 65.12, verbally described as basic achievement level, while the final assessment indicated a grand mean of 76.33, with a verbal description of proficient which shows that there is an increase in the students' achievement.

Initially, 52 out of the 66 learners got ratings/scores equivalent to basic achievement level and 14 scores equivalent to proficient level. After the school year long, modular instruction modality in delivering the curriculum content, 23 remained basic, while there were 42 proficient, and one (1) became advanced. However, the result indicates that the learners have not achieved yet the optimum expected learning outcome – advanced achievement level, which means that more actions have to be done.

Basically, most of the learners have manifested partial understanding of the lessons/subject matters, and that they needed closest teacher supervision as they process the content. Meanwhile, the 14 learners surfaced to have had solid academic performance and have understood the lessons and they could work independently or with little supervision from the teacher.

Also, towards the end of the school year, only a few remained basic, those who still have manifested partial understanding of the lessons/subject matters, and that they needed closest teacher supervision as they process the content while favorable percentage have shown how they have understood the lessons and they could work independently or with little supervision from the teacher. It was also good to know that one learner turned advanced for having manifested superior performance. He/she has had deep understanding on the topic reflected by having a good score in the final assessment.

The finding tells that the teacher must have to initiate other or another intervention in order to increase further the achievement of the learners, including improving the self-learning materials (modules) being given to learners for home study.

Generally, it can be deduced that through the modality of delivery of instruction, quantitative data prove the increase in learners' performance. Meaning, modular instruction did not at all deprive the learners from improving their academic achievements. Furthermore, various researches prove and assert that modular instruction equally works with other learning modalities.

The table displays that the attitudes of the learners in Quarter III has mean of 2.871, verbally described as agree, positive attitude and in Quarter IV, they have recorded a mean of 3.201, also agree, positive along attitude along teaching.

While the rest of the indicators gained means equivalent to agree and strongly agree, positive attitude, the fourth indicator, Electronics lessons bore me, gained an initial and final mean of 1.364, verbally described as strongly disagree, negative which means that the learners feel or behave otherwise. Meaning, they are not bored about electronics lessons.

The finding generally implies that the learners have been manifesting positive attitude about how Electronics lesson are being taught. They easily share learning problems; they are provided with help in the learning activities; they find joy and fun in their subject; and that they don't feel boredom in their Electronics subject. This further tells that the students have positive outlook and behavior about the subject and the topics that they learn from it.

The means in this particular indicator are 3.015 and 1.190, both verbally described as agree, positive. Most of the item indicators gained means which are equivalent to agree to strongly agree description, all positive attitude in Quarter III and Quarter IV.

However, item no. 4, I wish I were a student of another school gained the mean 1.364 in both quarters, verbally described as negative which means that the attitude of the learners is otherwise.

Meaning, the students do not wish that they were students of another school. The finding generally explains that the students have favorable attitude/feelings about the school image. They feel and believe positively to the school.

It is indeed conclusive to mean that the Electronics students sustained similar attitude from the beginning to the end of the school year. Modular learning has good implication to their performance even if the modality has been different with how they are used to. Modular learning worked good on them despite the total change of their norms and common practices while in the school in the previous school years. The new adjustments in the learning modality did not totally change the favorable behaviors of the learners towards education and learning.

It can be noticed that all the item indicators gained means which are equivalent to strongly disagree, negative descriptions resulting to 1.350 sub-mean at strongly disagree, negative descriptions too on both quarters.

The finding further tells that the students have manifested no measures of dismay or sadness along their subject so with their topics in Electronics, as well as with the teacher handling the same.

The table shows an initial mean of 3.470 and final mean of 3.708, verbally described as agree, positive and strongly agree/positive, respectively.

It can be seen that all the item indicators gained means equivalent to agree to strongly agree verbal indicators under attitude along testing and feedback which indicate the positive attitude of the students in both quarters of lesson delivery in Electronics under distance modular learning modality.

The results further imply a favorable behavior from among the learners at the very start up to the completion of this investigation.

The shows that the attitude of the learners along reluctance in both quarter are the same: 1.394, verbally described as strongly disagree, negative.

The result implies that the Electronics students' feel and manifest positive behavior. For them, communication within the family makes them feel more positive towards Electronics; their family consider their going to school necessary; negative attitudes of the people in my close circle towards school do not negatively affect their eagerness; they do not feel that as if I they are out of the activities in most of the courses; and they can participate in many activities in their Electronics class.

It is conclusive to note that the students have positive outlook and behavior towards their Electronic subject. It can be seen from the table that at first, the learners' attitude is negative as indicated by the grand mean of 2.373, and then turned positive after as shown by the grand mean of 2.516.

The summary definitely shows that the students have improved their attitudes towards the identified indicator and item indicators, a manifestation that distance modular learning did a favorable implication to the learners in studying Electronics.

It can be observed from the table the test indicated a computed t-value of -25.851, and critical t-value of 1.997, verbally described as significant at 0.05 alpha level.

It can be inferred from the finding that there is a significant difference in the Quarter III and Quarter IV achievements of the students in Electronics subjects which indicate further that there existed a favorable implication of distance modular learning modality from among the subjects of this study. Hence, distance modular learning modality can result to positive learning outcomes.

This finding is supported by Dangle and Sumaoang (2020) who claim, "The use of modules encourages independent study. One of the benefits of using modules for instruction is the acquisition of better self-study or learning skills among students. Students engage themselves in learning the concepts presented in the module. They develop a sense of responsibility in accomplishing the tasks provided in the module." They added, "Other advantages of modular instruction include more choice and self-pacing for students; more variety and flexibility for teachers and staff; and increased adaptability of instructional materials."

The test resulted to a computed t-value of -14.446 with a critical t-value of 1.997, verbally described as significant at 0.05 level of significance.

The finding tells that there is a significant difference in the students' attitude between the two quarters of lesson delivery in Electronics under the distance modular instruction modality. The result further implies that the modality has had favorable implication to the attitudes of the students under the Electronics class of the teacher-researcher.

The result is supported by the study of Sadiq and Zamir (2014) who dealt on the effectiveness of modular approach in teaching where the results were in the favor of use of modular teaching approach. Banking on the results, they recommended that the modular approach should be widely used at various levels of education.

Conclusions

Learners improve their achievement through the use of print materials, as well as the materials per se. Sense of responsibility and independency develop in them even with no to limited teacher-physical support to them since face-to-face instruction is not possible. While attitude and achievement are relative in many aspects, as proven in various studies and researches. Moreover, print modular instruction alone can possibly and positively effect to a learner.

In the light of the results of this research study, the following recommendations are offered: formative assessments such as pretest and diagnostic tests should be administered from among the learners which will eventually guide the teachers and the students themselves on how to deal with the contents while summative tests should be undertaken to make the teachers and the students reflect from their actions in dealing with the contents across learning areas. Teachers should encourage the learners to sustain positive outlook in life amid difficulties, as they gain academic growth from their scholastic engagements in school and in the comfort of their abodes with their families. Psychosocial and mental support should be given to the learners doing home-based studies. Subject teachers should not only rely on the DepEd-provided learning resources. They should also contextualize learning materials to suit the context of their learners to make learning more meaningful. They should supplement print materials with other modalities such as online, radio and

TV instruction, digital and digitized resources, and many more. Teachers handling Electronics subjects must have to contextualize learning materials in order for the students to be more engaged and they can acquire not only the competencies but also the life skills they deserve to acquire for their future lives. The teacher-researcher, so with other teachers, must enhance further the print materials prepared for learners' use so that optimized learning acquisition will be possible. Doing so will not only bring the learners to a proficient level, but higher, up to advanced level of achievement. School administrators should support teachers' initiatives in enhancing and in supplementing the curriculum, and in providing for what are needed in order to provide the best services to the school stakeholders, the learners, in particular. Parents and family members should scaffold the learners in dealing with challenging academic tasks in order for the latter to find motivation to keep going and develop in them love for work and studies despite the challenges of having no classroom-based education nowadays.

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